

SMS PLATFORM DATA LIMITATIONS

The SMS platform was designed to maximize survivor confidentiality and comfort in accessing services. Because users have full autonomy to choose what to share, data on demographics and nature of case are more limited.

It can be difficult to consistently track unique SMS users, as clients can contact WKF with different numbers or cancel their service to a particular mobile device at any point in time. Therefore, it is challenging to track their cases over time, accounting for the small number of referral information for SMS users, given that cases are only documented as "referred" if WKF can verify that their client has accessed the service.

The SMS data currently only tracks the location of an SMS user if they are in the Mukuru area, but not beyond that, so the reach of the SMS platform to other areas is not being captured formally.

WALK-IN DATA LIMITATIONS

Some data collected at walk-in visits is recorded on paper but not yet tracked electronically due to capacity limitations.

There may be human error involved in the recording of the walk-in data, as it is recorded first by hand and then manually entered electronically.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR WKF

- 1 Streamline WKF's data collection process and create an electronic client intake form to avoid transferring the data manually.
- 2 Refine the SMS platform so that it can capture location data beyond Mukuru to better understand WKF's reach and the SGBV 'hot spots.'
- 3 Increase the human resource capacity to service survivors, including those outside of Mukuru. Consider a mobile clinic or additional WKF sites to service all clientele more conveniently. With increased human resources support, WKF can also better track its cases. Trained members of @SSV_Ke could be great candidates for these additional positions.
- 4 Tap into the @SSV_Ke network to better service clients on the SMS platform. Particularly when cases turn up outside of Nairobi, survivors from @SSV_Ke in counties around Kenya can respond to those cases more easily and immediately. Additionally, they can direct survivors to relevant services vetted by WKF in their area.

Frankel A, Kanja W, Wood SN, Hameeduddin Z, Decker MR
 Research & Policy Brief. *The Wangu Kanja Foundation 2018 Data Review: Supporting SGBV Survivors via SMS and Traditional Direct Service.*
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 Johns Hopkins University, The Wangu Kanja Foundation, Action Aid
 Baltimore, MD, USA & Nairobi, Kenya

STRENGTHS OF WKF'S WORK

WKF's work is evidence-based and survivor-focused. Their clients' cases and referrals are tracked, and used to inform programming and strategic partnerships with service providers who can best serve the needs of their clients. Furthermore, the @SSV_Ke network is an important and powerful step towards deliberately and actively integrating survivors' perspectives into the SGBV justice process.

WKF is innovating the way organizations can support survivors and respond to instances of SGBV through the convenience and confidentiality of a national SMS platform that services people all throughout Kenya.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

WKF provides comprehensive, quality and accessible services to women, men and children in response to incidents of SGBV, including rape, defilement, physical abuse, and domestic violence. Complicated and unique cases are referred to their highly qualified, vetted partner organizations.

Given the sensitivity and stigmatization of SGBV, WKF has an SMS platform to provide clients across Kenya with a tool to anonymously and safely access services, helping them connect to WKF more immediately and conveniently.

WKF is putting survivors' voices into the forefront, both through their tracking of survivors' cases and needs, as well as through their @SSV_Ke network.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICY MAKERS & IMPLEMENTERS

- 1 Scale up the SMS system for accessing SGBV services. Survivors are clearly interested in using an SMS platform that allows confidential access to services, which can also provide 'real time' electronic data on survivors' cases and needs. A system like this can benefit survivors as well as implementors and policy-makers who can use the data to inform interventions and policies.
- 2 Incorporate the voices of survivors into the design of SGBV interventions by strengthening the partnership and interaction with survivors of @SSV_Ke. Engage survivors as active participants in the design of interventions and policies.
- 3 Increase government resources devoted to responding to survivor's needs, including more financial and human resource support in both number and SGBV expertise.
 - Prioritize allocating resources to mental health services and safe spaces for survivors.
 - WKF data shows how SGBV affects males and females alike. Develop more comprehensive resources inclusive of all survivors of SGBV, including boys and men.
- 4 Refine the investigative processes of SGBV cases to improve the chain of evidence against perpetrators and support survivors' pursuit of justice. Currently, no system exists to tie the DNA results from a medical examination of a survivor to a perpetrator.

The Wangu Kanja Foundation 2018 Data Review: Supporting SGBV Survivors via SMS and Traditional Direct Service

In 2005, Wangu Kanja, inspired to improve the services offered to survivors of sexual violence, established The Wangu Kanja Foundation (WKF), a not-for-profit organization registered as a Trustee under the Perpetual Succession Act Chapter 164 of the Laws of Kenya. Based in the Nairobi urban slum of Mukuru kwa Reuben, WKF provides comprehensive services to men, women and children across Kenya who have experienced sexual and gender based violence. Services include medical, psychological, psychosocial, and legal redress with the support of an extensive partnership network. Many service providers are located on their campus, which serves as a "one-stop-shop".

WKF has accepted walk-ins since 2005. In 2014, WKF began monitoring their cases. From 2014-May 2018, WKF received 423 walk-ins. In 2016, in partnership with Action Aid, WKF established an SMS platform to increase outreach and help survivors across Nairobi and beyond to connect to services anonymously. The SMS case load grew rapidly from 197 SMS responders in 2016, to 415 in 2017. As of May 2018, WKF has had 783 total SMS respondents reach out for either services, or to learn more about gender based violence.

In July 2017, WKF convened survivors of sexual violence across 47 counties in Kenya to serve as members of The Survivors of Sexual Violence in Kenya Network (@SSV_Ke). This network brings survivors together to support one another through the justice process. This network also unifies and amplifies their voices on the public stage, as they work to ensure that all duty-bearers are held accountable in the fight for justice for survivors of sexual and gender based violence (SGBV).

SGBV cases supported by WKF range widely, and include rape, defilement, domestic violence and physical abuse. The following case definitions are in line with The Sexual Offenses Act of 2006, revised in 2009 by Kenya's National Council for Law Reporting, and The Protection Against Domestic Violence Act of 2015.

Case Types	WKF's Case Definition
Rape	Any sexual violation against a person who is above 18 years of age that causes unlawful and intentional penetration with his or her genital organs.
Defilement	Any sexual violation which causes penetration with a person below the age of 18 years.
Physical Abuse	Any physical abuse against a person of any age.
Domestic Violence	Violence against a person, or threat of violence or of imminent danger to that person, by any other person with whom that person is, or has been, in a domestic relationship.

The primary cases that WKF supports are SGBV cases, comprising mostly of domestic violence, rape, defilement, and physical abuse cases. In addition to the GBV caseload, WKF receives a smaller number of other, non-SGBV related cases, such as child custody or school fee payment cases, which they also support and track. Due to WKF's extensive partnership network with quality, affordable service providers, they are able to refer these non-GBV cases to relevant services as well.

WKF CASELOAD BY PLATFORM

	SGBV Cases	Other, Non-SGBV Cases	Unknown Cases	Total Cases
Walk-Ins	321	101	1	423
SMS Users	149	124	510	783
Total Clients	470	225	511	1,206

Known vs. Unknown Cases: Not all walk-in or SMS users' cases are known. Due to WKF's protection and respect of its clients, the team can only classify cases if the survivor chooses to disclose their experience to the team. Therefore, in aggregate, from 2014-May 2018, of the total number of walk-ins and SMS users who reached out to WKF, 695 cases are known and have been identified, documented and tracked by WKF. Majority of known cases are walk-ins. The following table and graphs depict the type of cases actively supported and monitored by WKF, disaggregated by sex and whether the client was a walk-in or SMS user.

WKF's SMS Users' Known Case Types Disaggregated by Sex (2016-2018)
n=273

WKF's Walk-ins' Known Case Types Disaggregated by Sex (2014-2018)
n=422

WKF SERVICE PROVISION AND REFERRALS

WKF manages majority of their caseloads in-house. For cases that require additional or unique support, WKF refers to a variety of closely-held service providers, largely medical, legal and psychosocial services. Some women are referred to more than one service, depending on their needs.

Many clients wish to speak with the chief or police of their community. WKF walks women through the process, often connecting them to community health volunteers and community paralegals who help them navigate the situation.

The majority of WKF's clients are referred to medical facilities so that they may secure a formal report to document the incident of sexual or gender based violence, and to receive necessary medical attention, including treatment for sexually transmitted infections. A medical report can be obtained and is often helpful when seeking legal action.

WKF provides majority of the legal support to their clients, primarily via their in-house, paralegal staff. For cases requiring additional support, WKF refers to closely-held lawyers who are willing to take on pro-bono cases. Some clients even choose to take their cases to court. Cases considered "concluded" are the cases taken to court and settled or closed.

WKF provides survivors with access to trusted shelters; however, while the demand may be high for temporary safe spaces, it is difficult for WKF to place women above the age of 18 into shelters. Shelters are more likely to accept young girls and boys, than they are women or men, accounting for the small number referred.

WKF provides counseling services for their clients. A weekly counselor provides psychosocial support for women who are referred. Women requiring additional psychosocial support are referred to medical facilities with high-quality counseling programs.

WKF facilitates empowerment programs for many of their female clientele. About 100 women participate in WKF's livelihood training program, and about 10% of those women have been trained to develop a small peanut butter business, which can help them become more financially independent and less reliant on their partners.

WKF's Referrals to Walk-ins Disaggregated by Sex (2014-2018), n=1,052

WKF's Referrals to SMS Users Disaggregated by Sex (2016-2018), n=136

